

ISLAMIC FASHION OR MODEST FASHION?

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the role and place of modest fashion in the everyday lives of not only Muslim women but also all Eastern women in the context of fashion trends from leading global brands. The main similarities and contradictions with the norms of classical Islam are highlighted. Fashion trends in the collections of global brands that produce clothing compliant with both Islamic norms and contemporary fashion directions are showcased.*

Keywords: *fashion, hijab, tradition, woman, clothing, custom, mentality, culture, costume, modest fashion.*

Fashion is a well-forgotten old concept. As a rule, clothing items always return to everyday life after a certain period of time, but they come back updated, taking into account the trends of the modern world, including new elements. "We can consider fashion from various perspectives: as a way of dressing, as a socio-psychological function of culture, and as a mode of action. Alongside this, fashion can be interpreted as imitation of a certain image, as an expression of personal taste and uniqueness, and finally, as a way of life." Over the years, the same clothing can have different purposes. Its semantic and emotional significance changes depending on fashion trends and the spirit of the era. All these tendencies also affect national clothing, which serves as a kind of mirror reflecting various aspects of the cultural development of a people, recreating the stages of its historical journey.

If we look at the history of women's attire, we can notice that traditional clothing in many cultures around the world included long (floor-length) skirts and dresses, and head coverings always concealed the hair—even if they were not completely covered, the area around the crown was always covered. This zone was considered sacred, and women from all cultures covered it—some with scarves, some with hats, some with tubeteikas, and others with kokoshniks, etc. However, as a result of the processes of cultural globalization that have swept across the world, women have gained a certain degree of freedom. The process of emancipation began, along with the borrowing of values from Western European society into all regions of the world, which marked the liberation of women and the loss of national customs related to both ethnic traditions and attire.

In recent decades, Islamic fashion has been gaining momentum, and we increasingly see women in veils on the streets of villages and cities. Researcher R.Yu. Rakhmatullin, analyzing the translations of the Quran by I.Yu. Kratchkovsky, M.-N. Osmanov, V.M. Porokhova, E. Kuliyeu, G.S. Sablukov, Sh. Alyautdinov, as well as the translation of A. Sadetsky's tafsir of Muhammad Ali from English into Russian, concluded that there is one unifying idea in the verses of the Holy Scripture of Islam regarding women: a woman should not evoke a sense of accessibility for foreign men through her gaze and body. It is necessary to cover the neckline

from the view of strange men and not to display one's adornments hidden under clothing. However, what specifically, apart from this, relates to objects of desire can be interpreted in various ways. In the hadiths of the Prophet Muhammad, there are many sayings regarding modesty and shyness in women, which are interpreted as the wearing of modest clothing. For example, one hadith states that "In Paradise, people will seek the presence of the Lord, and Allah will grant special honor to those women who adhered to the norms of Muslim women's dress in their earthly lives." However, this issue remains quite contentious even in the works of well-known Islamic theologians.

At the end of the 20th century, processes of re-Islamization in society began. There was a return to the Muslim dress code, but taking into account regional characteristics and fashion trends. The clothing of Eastern women has its nuances; thus, despite the prescriptions of the Quran and Sunnah, women's clothing varies from region to region, influenced by traditional national attire—some places strictly adhere to all the tenets of Islam, while others deviate from them as much as possible.

In many regions of the country, jewelry such as earrings, rings, and pendants were fashionable and significant attributes for women. Carefully selected accessories harmoniously complemented the entire women's wardrobe. In recent years, the trend in jewelry has changed: more and more women dressed according to Islamic principles (where hair and the chest area are fully covered, making earrings invisible) have started wearing pendants, bracelets, watches, chains, and large rings on two or three fingers, similar to Arabic jewelry. Islamic fashion is modest fashion that dictates its own laws, which both Eastern and Western women follow; for example: long maxi or midi outfits with a loose fit, covered heads, and modest accessories.

Picture. 1. DKNY Fashion Show¹

¹ <https://www.vogue.com/fashion-shows/designer/dkny>

For example, DKNY (Donna Karan International Inc.) is a fashion house in New York specializing in fashion goods for men and women, founded in 1984 by Donna Karan. In 2014, it presented its first collection of long dresses made from flowing fabrics, long skirts, sports suits, long-sleeved blouses, coats, and leather jackets, naming the collection "Ramadan in Modest Fashion." A year later, the global brand Mango followed suit by launching a collection of jackets, kaftans, shirts, as well as elegant floor-length dresses and long skirts. The well-known Spanish brand Zara also released its collection, which included soft blue prints. In 2016, the fashion house Dolce Gabbana launched a collection of scarves and abayas adorned with floral motifs, delicate lace, and even lemon prints. The baton was picked up in 2017 by the popular British luxury brand Burberry, which released a collection of glamorous light and modest dresses and fashionable handbags. The sports brand Nike introduced a sports hijab made from breathable fabric with good air permeability. The Japanese brand Uniqlo also released a collection of Eastern clothing. An American luxury brand offers its customers long bright kaftans decorated with patterns. The global Swedish brand HM did not release a separate "Ramadan" or "Modest Fashion" collection but featured a Muslim woman in their advertising campaign to indicate that their clothing considers the interests and tastes of all consumers. The giant US department store Macy's, in collaboration with Verona Collection, launched a collection of clothing including long dresses, loose cardigans, and trousers for Muslim women.

Fashion designers in the country are specializing in the tailoring and production of fashionable yet modest clothing, and their numbers are growing year by year, just as the number of "modest" women in the country and around the world is increasing. Demand generates supply, and the number of popular Russian Muslim brands such as Sahara, Irada, Hayat, Sabr, and others is on the rise. Caucasian designers are also making their mark, becoming known in the region, the country, and even globally. Their popularity is largely due to the production of clothing that adheres to Islamic norms. They consistently hold leading positions in this cluster of Muslim fashion. Among them are Aida Arashukova, Aisha and Madina Arshaevy, Zaira Getagazheva, Leila and Fatima Oskanova, Aishat Kadyrova, Fatima Khachilaeva, and many others.

Islamic fashion or MODEST FASHION has become a part of the creative journey for the owners of such salons. They participate in the most famous fashion weeks, bringing national color to their clothing designs.

Fashion houses from Chechnya, such as Firdaws and Aset, are very popular in Uzbekistan. The leader in this cluster is the Firdaws trading house, founded by the First Lady of the Chechen Republic, Medni Kadyrova. Firdaws is a Chechen brand with collections that strongly reflect folk motifs. Historically, local girls wore headscarves and long dresses, so the brand's collections also represent a revival of national style. The decor on the clothing and fitted silhouettes are modern interpretations of the image of a mountain girl. However, Firdaws collections also feature flowing silhouettes and gentle shades. "Fashion, when entering a multi-ethnic society, passes through a prism of the region's ethnic uniqueness. Undoubtedly, there is an exchange between mass fashion and seemingly closed traditions."

The Aset fashion house, founded by Aiza Jabrailova, is also very popular; outfits from her collections are worn by both Saudi princesses and businesswomen. Many designers believe that a well-tailored modest outfit can be stylish and beautiful, appealing to girls "both in Islam and outside of it."

An ethnic component can be traced in fashion regarding headscarves and turbans depending on fashion trends and seasons. For example, local girls in Uzbekistan adorn their outfits with rhinestones, sequins, and lace. They actively use both bright solid fabrics and floral prints for dressmaking. Local embroidery also prevails here. We see that ethnic components are added to fashion requirements, creating a unique local flavor.

Today, there is a wide variety of women's headwear and coverings. Generally, common norms are adjusted according to the customs of the country and region and can be stricter or looser; however, the most important aspect here is modesty—not only of the fashionable woman herself but also of her outfit.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the diversity of women's headwear, outfits, and accessories reflects the cultural traditions and customs of various countries and regions. Modesty, as an important aspect, plays a key role in image selection, emphasizing respect for cultural norms and values. Thus, modest fashion becomes not only a fashion statement but also a symbol of identity and belonging to a particular culture. It is important to remember that style can coexist with respect for traditions, creating a harmonious image.

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